

Appendix A: Supplementary tables and figures

Table A.1. Lines of SiO, CS, and SiS detected in this study.

Star	Molecule	Transition	ν_{calc} (MHz)	ν_{obs} (MHz)	V_{exp} (km s ⁻¹)	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)
R Leo	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	–	–	3.9 ^a
	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86847.0(2)	5.0(2)	16.1(16)
	SiO	J=6-5	260517.985	260517.8(2)	5.2(2)	43(13)
	SiO	J=7-6	303926.783	303926.4(3)	4.9(3)	49(15)
	CS	J=5-4	244935.554	244935.2(3)	4.8(3)	0.41(12)
	CS	J=6-5	293912.089	293911.9(3)	4.7(3)	0.59(18)
R Cas	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	–	–	10.2 ^a
	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	–	–	28.3 ^a
	SiO	J=6-5	260517.985	–	–	53.7 ^a
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97979.8(8)	7.1(10)	0.10(1)
	CS	J=5-4	244935.554	244935.1(6)	7.8(7)	0.84(25)
	SiS	J=14-13	254103.211	254102.5(8)	9.1(10)	0.92(28)
TX Cam	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	–	–	10.4 ^a
	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86847.1(2)	18.5(6)	30.4(30)
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97981.0(1)	17.1(2)	1.69(17)
IK Tau V1111 Oph	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	–	–	24.8 ^a
	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	–	–	6.4 ^a
	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86847.0(2)	15.9(3)	12.8(13)
	SiO	J=6-5	260517.985	260517.7(2)	15.5(3)	19.4(58)
	SiO	J=7-6	303926.783	303926.0(4)	15.9(6)	24.5(73)
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97981.6(8)	13.1(8)	0.32(3)
	CS	J=5-4	244935.554	244935.9(5)	13.9(8)	1.93(58)
	CS	J=6-5	293912.089	293912.9(10)	14.5(10)	2.88(86)
	SiS	J=14-13	254103.211	254103.5(5)	13.7(9)	3.00(90)
	SiS	J=16-15	290380.744	290381.6(10)	14.2(10)	4.7(14)
	SiS	J=17-16	308516.144	308515.5(10)	13.3(10)	4.3(13)
GX Mon	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	–	–	9.9 ^a
	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86847.1(2)	18.5(6)	23.1(23)
	SiO	J=6-5	260517.985	260517.6(3)	18.0(5)	29.1(87)
	SiO	J=7-6	303926.783	303926.4(3)	17.6(6)	31.7(95)
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97981.0(1)	18.0(2)	0.75(8)
	CS	J=5-4	244935.554	244935.7(3)	16.6(6)	3.4(10)
	CS	J=6-5	293912.089	293912.8(10)	17.1(10)	3.4(10)
	SiS	J=14-13	254103.211	254103.2(2)	18.4(6)	4.2(12)
	SiS	J=16-15	290380.744	290380.6(3)	16.3(8)	4.4(13)
	SiS	J=17-16	308516.144	308517.1(10)	16.4(10)	4.0(12)
	NV Aur	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	–	–
SiO		J=2-1	86846.971	86846.9(1)	17.9(3)	7.61(76)
SiO		J=6-5	260517.985	260517.3(3)	17.1(3)	12.7(38)
CS		J=2-1	97980.952	97981.0(3)	16.5(5)	0.31(3)
CS		J=5-4	244935.554	244935.2(5)	16.5(8)	1.76(53)
SiS		J=14-13	254103.211	254102.4(4)	18.0(4)	5.3(16)
Y CVn	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86847.0(2)	6.7(5)	0.16(2)
	SiO	J=7-6	303926.783	303928.2(15)	7.1(10)	1.08(33)
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97981.0(2)	8.3(4)	1.80(18)
R Lep	CS	J=6-5	293912.089	293912.2(4)	7.7(5)	10.3(31)
	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	43423.9(3)	16.8(10)	0.26(3)
	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86846.4(4)	21.1(10)	1.22(12)
	SiO	J=6-5	260517.985	260516.5(8)	18.6(10)	8.2(25)
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97980.4(4)	20.2(10)	1.46(15)
LP And	CS	J=5-4	244935.554	244934.5(4)	19.0(10)	14.0(42)
	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	43423.9(1)	13.1(2)	0.89(9)
	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86846.8(2)	12.9(4)	3.09(31)
	SiO	J=6-5	260517.985	260517.5(3)	14.5(4)	8.5(26)
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97980.9(2)	12.9(4)	14.2(14)
	CS	J=5-4	244935.554	244935.4(3)	13.7(4)	31.2(94)
IRC +20370	SiS	J=2-1	36309.629	36309.7(1)	13.0(2)	0.30(3)
	SiS	J=14-13	254103.211	–	–	15.7 ^a
	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	43423.8(2)	14.1(5)	0.57(6)
	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86846.9(2)	12.9(5)	3.08(31)
	SiO	J=6-5	260517.985	260517.7(3)	13.8(4)	17.3(52)
	SiO	J=7-6	303926.783	303926.4(3)	13.4(4)	19.4(58)
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97981.0(2)	12.6(8)	7.74(77)

Table A.1. continued.

Star	Molecule	Transition	ν_{calc} (MHz)	ν_{obs} (MHz)	V_{exp} (km s ⁻¹)	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)
	CS	J=5-4	244935.554	244935.2(3)	13.3(7)	45(13)
	CS	J=6-5	293912.089	293911.7(4)	14.1(7)	41(12)
	SiS	J=14-13	254103.211	–	–	16.8 ^a
	SiS	J=16-15	290380.744	290380.4(4)	12.9(8)	14.3(43)
	SiS	J=17-16	308516.144	308516.0(7)	12.2(10)	13.0(39)
IRC +30374	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86846.9(2)	21.9(6)	3.69(37)
	SiO	J=6-5	260517.985	260517.6(4)	26.1(8)	14.2(42)
	SiO	J=7-6	303926.783	303925.7(6)	26.0(10)	18.6(56)
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97980.6(3)	23.0(8)	15.6(16)
	CS	J=5-4	244935.554	244935.0(4)	23.6(8)	42(13)
	CS	J=6-5	293912.089	293911.2(5)	25.1(8)	48(14)
	SiS	J=14-13	254103.211	254102.5(7)	21.7(10)	5.4(16)
	SiS	J=16-15	290380.744	290380.2(6)	23.8(10)	7.8(23)
	SiS	J=17-16	308516.144	308514.8(10)	24.5(12)	5.2(16)
IRC +10216	SiO	J=1-0	43423.844	43423.8(1)	14.4(1)	15.4(15)
	CS	J=1-0	48990.957	48990.9(1)	14.0(1)	45.0(45)
	SiS	J=2-1	36309.629	36309.6(1)	14.1(1)	9.08(91)
CRL190	SiO	J=2-1	86846.971	86846.8(10)	13.1(10)	0.19(2)
	CS	J=1-0	48990.957	48990.7(3)	13.7(10)	0.83(8)
	CS	J=2-1	97980.952	97980.9(2)	14.7(7)	3.90(39)
	CS	J=5-4	244935.554	244935.1(5)	14.1(7)	8.7(26)
	CS	J=6-5	293912.089	293911.3(5)	14.2(8)	7.1(21)
	SiS	J=14-13	254103.211	254103.3(10)	12.8(10)	1.67(50)
	SiS	J=16-15	290380.744	290380.0(8)	13.6(10)	2.06(62)

^a Line is not fitted due to a complex line profile. Only velocity-integrated intensity is given.

Fig. A.1. Lines of SiO, CS, and SiS detected in this study (see parameters in Table A.1) ordered from top to bottom and from left to right. The velocity resolution has been smoothed to ~ 2 km s⁻¹ for better visualization.

Fig. A.1. continued.

Fig. A.1. continued.

Table A.2. Continuum flux data.

λ (μm)	Flux (Jy)	Catalog									
R Leo			R Cas			TX Cam			IK Tau		
1.24	7940	2MASS	1.24	1360	2MASS	1.24	205	2MASS	0.96	55	PAN-STARRS
1.26	4280	DIRBE	1.26	2090	DIRBE	1.26	380	DIRBE	1.24	325	2MASS
1.65	5280	2MASS	1.65	2300	2MASS	1.65	495	2MASS	1.65	981	2MASS
2.16	5610	2MASS	2.16	2460	2MASS	2.16	683	2MASS	2.16	1600	2MASS
2.22	7280	DIRBE	2.22	3490	DIRBE	2.22	981	DIRBE	2.22	1110	DIRBE
3.35	3680	unWISE	3.35	1880	unWISE	3.35	884	unWISE	3.52	1530	DIRBE
3.52	5640	DIRBE	3.52	2590	DIRBE	3.52	901	DIRBE	4.60	1900	unWISE
4.60	4020	unWISE	4.60	2250	unWISE	4.60	1160	unWISE	4.89	1740	DIRBE
11.6	2070	IRAS	4.89	1750	DIRBE	4.89	675	DIRBE	11.6	4630	IRAS
22.1	673	WISE	11.6	1260	IRAS	11.6	514	allWISE	22.1	1870	WISE
23.9	625	IRAS	22.1	706	WISE	18.4	508	AKARI	23.9	2380	IRAS
61.8	114	IRAS	23.9	543	IRAS	22.1	285	allWISE	61.8	332	IRAS
102	39.3	IRAS	61.8	102	IRAS	23.9	635	IRAS	102	103	IRAS
			65	82.7	AKARI	61.8	134	IRAS	855	0.25	SCUBA
			90	55.4	AKARI	102	38.6	IRAS			
			102	38.8	IRAS						
			140	10.8	AKARI						
			160	6.78	AKARI						
V1111 Oph			GX Mon			NV Aur			Y CVn		
0.96	8.73	PAN-STARRS	0.96	10.2	PAN-STARRS	0.96	0.32	PAN-STARRS	1.24	634	2MASS
1.24	35.4	2MASS	1.24	49.2	2MASS	1.24	0.833	2MASS	1.26	704	DIRBE
1.65	125	2MASS	1.65	123	2MASS	1.26	7.0	DIRBE	1.65	1360	2MASS
2.16	239	2MASS	2.16	201	2MASS	1.65	5.14	2MASS	2.16	1330	2MASS
3.35	370	unWISE	3.35	428	unWISE	2.16	19.0	2MASS	2.22	1240	DIRBE
4.60	648	unWISE	4.60	692	unWISE	2.22	32.0	DIRBE	3.35	934	unWISE
11.6	452	allWISE	8.61	275	AKARI	3.35	70.4	unWISE	3.52	931	DIRBE
18.4	483	AKARI	11.6	387	allWISE	3.52	117	DIRBE	4.60	835	unWISE
22.1	388	WISE	18.4	260	AKARI	4.89	168	DIRBE	4.89	336	DIRBE
23.9	318	IRAS	22.1	172	allWISE	8.61	259	AKARI	8.61	304	AKARI
61.8	66.0	IRAS	23.9	360	IRAS	11.6	177	allWISE	11.6	193	WISE
65	65.6	AKARI	61.8	106	IRAS	18.4	349	AKARI	18.4	91.7	AKARI
90	36.2	AKARI	65	76.5	AKARI	22.1	157	allWISE	22.1	57	WISE
102	22.7	IRAS	90	43.8	AKARI	23.9	274	IRAS	23.9	70.3	IRAS
140	9.55	AKARI	102	40.4	IRAS	61.8	72.4	IRAS	61.8	17.2	IRAS
160	6.14	AKARI	140	16.5	AKARI	102	23.0	IRAS	102	7.82	IRAS
			160	8.0	AKARI						
R Lep			LP And			IRC +20370			IRC +30374		
1.24	216	2MASS	1.24	0.223	2MASS	1.24	8.18	2MASS	1.24	0.406	2MASS
1.26	130	DIRBE	1.65	3.01	2MASS	1.65	44.0	2MASS	1.65	3.54	2MASS
1.65	465	2MASS	2.16	19.3	2MASS	2.16	134	2MASS	2.16	16.9	2MASS
2.16	616	2MASS	3.35	104	unWISE	2.22	186	DIRBE	3.35	154	unWISE
3.35	689	unWISE	4.60	603	unWISE	3.35	349	unWISE	4.29	291	MSX
3.52	549	DIRBE	11.6	445	allWISE	3.52	447	DIRBE	4.35	255	MSX
4.60	1080	unWISE	18.4	582	AKARI	4.60	846	allWISE	4.60	457	unWISE
4.89	493	DIRBE	22.1	207	allWISE	4.89	653	DIRBE	8.61	822	AKARI
11.6	279	WISE	61.8	112	IRAS	8.61	433	AKARI	11.6	325	DIRBE
18.4	140	AKARI	102	32.4	IRAS	11.6	283	WISE	12.1	361	MSX
22.1	123	WISE				18.4	296	AKARI	14.6	240	MSX
23.9	113	IRAS				22.1	231	WISE	18.4	186	AKARI
61.8	24.9	IRAS				23.9	293	IRAS	21.3	156	MSX
102	9.69	IRAS				61.8	54.3	IRAS	23.9	170	DIRBE
						65	63.9	AKARI	61.8	39	DIRBE
						90	24.4	AKARI	65	30.7	AKARI
						102	20.3	IRAS	90	17.1	AKARI
						140	8.27	AKARI	102	13.5	DIRBE
						160	4.09	AKARI	140	4.91	AKARI
									160	4.48	AKARI
IRC +10216			CRL 190								
0.96	0.356	ATLAS	3.35	0.323	allWISE						
0.96	0.587	PAN-STARRS	4.60	4.34	unWISE						
1.24	2.67	2MASS	8.28	56.5	MSX						
1.65	76.9	2MASS	8.61	75.5	AKARI						
2.16	475	2MASS	11.6	110	allWISE						
3.35	1330	unWISE	12.1	115	MSX						
4.60	9000	unWISE	14.6	138	MSX						
11.6	47500	DIRBE	18.4	197	AKARI						
23.9	23100	DIRBE	21.3	146	MSX						
61.8	5650	DIRBE	22.1	149	allWISE						
102	922	DIRBE	23.9	206	IRAS						
350	68	PLANCK	61.8	64.7	IRAS						
550	24.4	PLANCK	102	15.9	IRAS						
849	8.34	PLANCK									
1380	3.85	PLANCK									

Fluxes obtained from the VizieR database (Ochsenbein et al. 2000) at <http://vizier.cds.unistra.fr/vizier/sed/>.

References: IRAS (Beichman et al. 1988), PAN-STARSS (Chambers et al. 2019; Flewelling et al. 2019), MSX (Price et al. 2001; Egan et al. 2003), AKARI (Ishihara et al. 2010); unWISE (Lang 2104); allWISE (Mainzer et al. 2011); WISE (Mainzer et al. 2011; Meisner et al. 2016, 2017; Wright et al. 2010), DIRBE (Price et al. 2010; Smith et al. 2004), 2MASS (Skrutskie et al. 2006).

Fig. A.2. Results from SED analysis for all envelopes except IK Tau and IRC +10216 (shown in Fig. 1). The left panels show the observed fluxes in blue (see Table A.2) and the calculated SED from the best dusty model in red. The right panels show χ^2 as a function of the temperature at the dust condensation radius, T_c , and the logarithm of the optical depth at $10 \mu\text{m}$, $\log \tau_{10}$. The white contours correspond to 1, 2, and 3σ levels.

Fig. A.2. continued.

Fig. A.2. continued.

Table A.3. Summary of CO observations included in the analysis.

Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference	Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference	Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference
R Leo			R Cas			TX Cam		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	4.1	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	29.1	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	20.0	OSO (5)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	28.5	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	56.5	JCMT (2)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	61.0	JCMT (5)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	33.5	APEX (2)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	99.0	JCMT (2)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	71.0	JCMT (5)
<i>J</i> = 4-3	28.1	CSO (1)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	110.0	JCMT (2)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	149.0	JCMT (5)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	5.86	HIFI (1)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	14.7	HIFI (4)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	14.2	HIFI (4)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	38.1	CSO (2)	<i>J</i> = 10-9	11.8	HIFI (4)	<i>J</i> = 10-9	9.7	HIFI (4)
<i>J</i> = 9-8	8.35	HIFI (1)	<i>J</i> = 16-15	5.5	HIFI (4)			
IK Tau			V1111 Oph			GX Mon		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	59.42	IRAM (6)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	47.2	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	64.2	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	194.01	IRAM (6)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	82.1	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	128.1	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	246.13	IRAM (6)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	59.1	JCMT (7)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	80.0	JCMT (5)
<i>J</i> = 4-3	127.27	JCMT (2)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	46.1	APEX (1)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	79.0	JCMT (5)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	11.6	HIFI (4)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	3.13	HIFI (1)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	5.83	HIFI (1)
<i>J</i> = 7-6	122.61	APEX (2)	<i>J</i> = 9-8	2.50	HIFI (1)	<i>J</i> = 9-8	4.07	HIFI (1)
<i>J</i> = 10-9	10.7	HIFI (4)						
<i>J</i> = 16-15	12.9	HIFI (4)						
NV Aur			Y CVn			R Lep		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	43.3	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	9.1	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	32.5	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	59.1	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	24.6	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	100.3	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	38.8	JCMT (2)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	20.9	JCMT (8)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	32.3	APEX (1)
<i>J</i> = 4-3	35.4	JCMT (2)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	17.0	CSO (1)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	36.6	APEX (1)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	2.54	HIFI (1)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	16.9	CSO (1)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	4.23	HIFI (1)
<i>J</i> = 9-8	1.84	HIFI (1)				<i>J</i> = 9-8	4.57	HIFI (1)
LP And			IRC +20370			IRC +30374		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	83.9	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	82.8	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	54.4	IRAM (9)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	153.6	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	136.5	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	110.5	IRAM (9)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	67.6	JCMT (2)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	60.3	APEX (2)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	38.3	JCMT (10)
<i>J</i> = 4-3	74.2	JCMT (2)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	66.1	APEX (2)			
<i>J</i> = 6-5	54.9	CSO (2)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	6.32	HIFI (1)			
			<i>J</i> = 7-6	49.8	APEX (2)			
			<i>J</i> = 9-8	7.46	HIFI (1)			
IRC +10216			CRL 190					
<i>J</i> = 1-0	446.2	IRAM (11)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	31.0	IRAM (9)			
<i>J</i> = 2-1	919.4	IRAM (11)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	42.7	IRAM (9)			
<i>J</i> = 3-2	1573.	IRAM (11)						
<i>J</i> = 4-3	639.17	CSO (2)						
<i>J</i> = 5-4	246.7	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 6-5	271.6	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 7-6	283.6	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 8-7	314.2	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 9-8	324.3	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 10-9	340.2	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 11-10	322.3	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 13-12	325.0	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 14-13	364.6	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 15-14	335.8	HIFI (11)						
<i>J</i> = 16-15	345.0	HIFI (11)						

References: (1) Danilovich et al. (2015). (2) De Beck et al. (2010). (3) Neri et al. (1998). (4) Justanont et al. (2012). (5) Ramstedt et al. (2008). (6) Velilla-Prieto et al. (2017). (7) Ramstedt & Olofsson (2014). (8) Schöier & Olofsson (2001). (9) This work. (10) JCMT archive. (11) J. Cernicharo (priv. comm.).

Fig. A.3. Results from CO analysis for all envelopes except IK Tau and IRC +10216 (shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3). The left panels show the observed velocity-integrated intensities as black filled circles (see Table A.3) and the calculated ones as red empty circles. The right panels show χ^2 as a function of the logarithm of the mass-loss rate, $\log \dot{M}$, and the exponent of the gas kinetic temperature radial profile, δ . The white contours correspond to 1, 2, and 3 σ levels.

Fig. A.3. continued.

Fig. A.3. continued.

Table A.4. Summary of SiO, CS, and SiS observations included in the analysis.

Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference	Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference	Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference
R Leo								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	3.9	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	0.10	IRAM (3)			
<i>J</i> = 2-1	16.1	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	0.41	IRAM (1)			
<i>J</i> = 2-1	5.10	OSO (6)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	0.59	IRAM (1)			
<i>J</i> = 2-1	4.90	SEST (6)						
<i>J</i> = 3-2	25.6	IRAM (3)						
<i>J</i> = 5-4	10.8	SEST (6)						
<i>J</i> = 6-5	43	IRAM (1)						
<i>J</i> = 7-6	49	IRAM (1)						
R Cas								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	10.2	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.10	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	0.18	IRAM (3)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	28.3	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	0.32	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 14-13	0.92	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	8.60	OSO (6)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	0.84	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 19-18	0.80	JCMT (11)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	31.9	IRAM (3)						
<i>J</i> = 5-4	7.2	SMT (8)						
<i>J</i> = 6-5	53.7	IRAM (1)						
<i>J</i> = 8-7	15.0	SMT (8)						
TX Cam								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	10.4	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	1.69	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	1.80	IRAM (9)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	30.4	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	1.00	OSO (10)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	0.60	OSO (10)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	13.2	OSO (6)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	3.06	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	0.80	OSO (11)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	36.4	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	3.8	IRAM (9)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	2.87	IRAM (3)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	9.6	SMT (8)				<i>J</i> = 12-11	1.50	JCMT (11)
<i>J</i> = 8-7	11.6	SMT (8)						
IK Tau								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	24.8	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.93	IRAM (4)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	1.19	IRAM (4)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	36.0	IRAM (4)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.50	OSO (10)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	2.44	IRAM (4)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	16.1	OSO (6)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	3.11	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	6.1	IRAM (3)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	56	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	1.46	APEX (13)	<i>J</i> = 9-8	7.7	IRAM (4)
<i>J</i> = 4-3	66	IRAM (4)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	9.7	IRAM (4)	<i>J</i> = 12-11	14.3	IRAM (4)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	91	IRAM (4)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	10.8	IRAM (4)	<i>J</i> = 12-11	4.7	JCMT (11)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	18.9	SEST (6)	<i>J</i> = 7-6	12.4	IRAM (4)	<i>J</i> = 12-11	3.4	APEX (13)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	16.5	SMT (8)	<i>J</i> = 7-6	2.57	APEX (13)	<i>J</i> = 13-12	18.1	IRAM (4)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	101	IRAM (4)				<i>J</i> = 14-13	20.4	IRAM (4)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	13.7	SEST (6)				<i>J</i> = 14-13	4.3	APEX (13)
<i>J</i> = 7-6	110	IRAM (4)				<i>J</i> = 16-15	23.9	IRAM (4)
<i>J</i> = 8-7	98	IRAM (4)				<i>J</i> = 17-16	20.3	IRAM (4)
						<i>J</i> = 19-18	28.1	IRAM (4)
						<i>J</i> = 19-18	9.2	JCMT (11)
						<i>J</i> = 19-18	5.6	APEX (13)
V1111 Oph								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	6.4	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.32	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	2.17	IRAM (3)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	12.8	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	1.18	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 14-13	3.00	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	6.30	OSO (6)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	1.93	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 16-15	4.7	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	21.0	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	2.88	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 17-16	4.3	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	5.3	SMT (8)						
<i>J</i> = 6-5	19.4	IRAM (1)						
<i>J</i> = 7-6	24.5	IRAM (1)						
<i>J</i> = 8-7	3.8	SMT (8)						
GX Mon								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	9.9	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.75	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	1.04	IRAM (14)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	23.1	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	1.51	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	2.10	IRAM (3)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	9.40	OSO (6)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	0.94	APEX (13)	<i>J</i> = 12-11	1.40	JCMT (11)

Table A.4. continued.

Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference	Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference	Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference
<i>J</i> = 2-1	5.50	SEST (6)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	3.4	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 12-11	1.03	APEX (13)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	25.0	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	3.4	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 14-13	4.2	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	8.9	SEST (6)	<i>J</i> = 7-6	0.71	APEX (13)	<i>J</i> = 14-13	0.85	APEX (13)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	3.8	SMT (8)				<i>J</i> = 16-15	4.4	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	29.1	IRAM (1)				<i>J</i> = 17-16	4.0	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 7-6	31.7	IRAM (1)				<i>J</i> = 19-18	1.02	APEX (13)
<i>J</i> = 8-7	3.4	SMT (8)						
NV Aur								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	5.1	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.31	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	0.65	OSO (11)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	7.61	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	0.77	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	1.25	IRAM (14)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	13.7	IRAM (3)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	1.76	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	2.98	IRAM (3)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	1.52	SMT (8)				<i>J</i> = 12-11	1.50	JCMT (11)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	12.7	IRAM (1)				<i>J</i> = 14-13	5.3	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 8-7	3.04	SMT (8)						
Y CVn								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.16	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	1.80	IRAM (1)			
<i>J</i> = 3-2	0.38	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.70	OSO (10)			
<i>J</i> = 7-6	1.08	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	5.5	IRAM (2)			
			<i>J</i> = 6-5	10.3	IRAM (1)			
R Lep								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	0.26	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	1.46	IRAM (1)			
<i>J</i> = 2-1	1.22	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	5.8	IRAM (2)			
<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.39	SEST (7)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	2.30	APEX (13)			
<i>J</i> = 3-2	3.45	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	14.0	IRAM (1)			
<i>J</i> = 3-2	0.99	SEST (7)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	4.1	APEX (13)			
<i>J</i> = 5-4	3.26	SEST (7)						
<i>J</i> = 6-5	8.2	IRAM (1)						
<i>J</i> = 8-7	2.73	APEX (7)						
LP And								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	0.89	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	14.2	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.30	Yebes (1)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	3.09	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	9.56	OSO (12)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	4.20	IRAM (9)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.94	OSO (12)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	35.6	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	1.80	OSO (11)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	8.6	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	31.2	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	1.91	OSO (12)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	0.62	ARO (7)				<i>J</i> = 7-6	7.0	IRAM (2)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	2.76	ARO (7)				<i>J</i> = 8-7	12.3	IRAM (2)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	8.5	IRAM (1)				<i>J</i> = 14-13	15.7	IRAM (1)
IRC +20370								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	0.57	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	7.74	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	1.33	IRAM (14)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	3.08	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	19.9	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 7-6	3.10	IRAM (2)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	7.2	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	6.0	APEX (13)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	5.6	IRAM (2)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	17.3	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	45	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 9-8	1.66	APEX (13)
<i>J</i> = 7-6	19.4	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	41	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 12-11	2.39	APEX (13)
			<i>J</i> = 6-5	10.8	APEX (13)	<i>J</i> = 14-13	16.8	IRAM (1)
			<i>J</i> = 7-6	9.6	APEX (13)	<i>J</i> = 16-15	14.3	IRAM (1)
						<i>J</i> = 16-15	3.6	APEX (13)
						<i>J</i> = 17-16	13.0	IRAM (1)
						<i>J</i> = 19-18	3.27	APEX (13)
IRC +30374								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 2-1	3.69	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	15.6	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 7-6	1.83	IRAM (2)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	7.1	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	26.7	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	2.99	IRAM (2)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	14.2	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	42	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 14-13	5.4	IRAM (1)
<i>J</i> = 7-6	18.6	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	48	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 16-15	7.8	IRAM (1)
						<i>J</i> = 17-16	5.2	IRAM (1)

Table A.4. continued.

Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference	Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference	Line	$\int T_{\text{mb}} dv$ (K km s ⁻¹)	Telescope Reference
IRC +10216								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 1-0	15.4	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	45.0	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	9.08	Yebes (1)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	60.1	IRAM (5)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	137	IRAM (5)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	114	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	21.7	SEST (7)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	130	OSO (10)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	60.0	OSO (11)
<i>J</i> = 2-1	29.9	OSO (10)	<i>J</i> = 3-2	379	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	106	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	131	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 4-3	407	IRAM (5)	<i>J</i> = 7-6	163	IRAM (2)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	27.9	ARO (7)	<i>J</i> = 5-4	518	IRAM (5)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	271	IRAM (2)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	48.4	SEST (7)	<i>J</i> = 6-5	778	IRAM (5)	<i>J</i> = 9-8	335	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 4-3	206	IRAM (5)	<i>J</i> = 7-6	607	IRAM (5)	<i>J</i> = 10-9	245	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	221	IRAM (5)				<i>J</i> = 11-10	343	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	84	SEST (7)				<i>J</i> = 12-11	272	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 5-4	68	SMT (8)				<i>J</i> = 13-12	350	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 6-5	288	IRAM (5)				<i>J</i> = 14-13	525	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 7-6	334	IRAM (5)				<i>J</i> = 15-14	621	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 8-7	367	IRAM (5)				<i>J</i> = 16-15	590	IRAM (5)
<i>J</i> = 8-7	101	SMT (8)				<i>J</i> = 17-16	365	IRAM (5)
						<i>J</i> = 18-17	500	IRAM (5)
						<i>J</i> = 19-18	459	IRAM (5)
						<i>J</i> = 20-19	160	APEX (11)
CRL190								
SiO			CS			SiS		
<i>J</i> = 2-1	0.19	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 1-0	0.83	Yebes (1)	<i>J</i> = 7-6	1.45	IRAM (2)
<i>J</i> = 3-2	0.39	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 2-1	3.90	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 8-7	1.93	IRAM (2)
			<i>J</i> = 3-2	6.8	IRAM (2)	<i>J</i> = 14-13	1.67	IRAM (1)
			<i>J</i> = 5-4	8.7	IRAM (1)	<i>J</i> = 16-15	2.06	IRAM (1)
			<i>J</i> = 6-5	7.1	IRAM (1)			

References: (1) This work. (2) Massalkhi et al. (2019). (3) Massalkhi et al. (2020). (4) Velilla-Prieto et al. (2017). (5) Agúndez et al. (2012). (6) González Delgado et al. (2003). (7) Schöier et al. (2006a). (8) Bieging et al. (2000). (9) Bujarrabal et al. (1994). (10) Olofsson et al. (1998). (11) Schöier et al. (2007). (12) Woods et al. (2003). (13) Danilovich et al. (2018). (14) Danilovich et al. (2015). ^a Values have been revised with respect to those given in the original reference.

Fig. A.4. Results from SiO analysis for all envelopes except IK Tau and IRC +10216 (shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). The left panels show the observed velocity-integrated intensities as black filled circles (see Table A.4) and the calculated ones as red empty circles. The right panels show χ^2 as a function of the logarithm of the fractional abundance of SiO relative to H_2 , $\log f_0$, and the logarithm of the e -folding radius, $\log r_e$. The white contours correspond to 1, 2, and 3 σ levels.

Fig. A.4. continued.

Fig. A.4. continued.

Fig. A.5. Results from CS analysis for all envelopes except IK Tau and IRC +10216 (shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). The left panels show the observed velocity-integrated intensities as black filled circles (see Table A.4) and the calculated ones as red empty circles. The right panels show χ^2 as a function of the logarithm of the fractional abundance of CS relative to H_2 , $\log f_0$, and the logarithm of the e -folding radius, $\log r_e$. The white contours correspond to 1, 2, and 3 σ levels.

Fig. A.5. continued.

Fig. A.5. continued.

Fig. A.6. Results from SiS analysis for all envelopes except IK Tau and IRC +10216 (shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). The left panels show the observed velocity-integrated intensities as black filled circles (see Table A.4) and the calculated ones as red empty circles. The right panels show χ^2 as a function of the logarithm of the fractional abundance of SiS relative to H_2 , $\log f_0$, and the logarithm of the e -folding radius, $\log r_e$. The white contours correspond to 1, 2, and 3 σ levels.

Fig. A.6. continued.

Fig. A.6. continued.